

Application of Remote Accessibility System & Automated Fault Analysis System for fault analysis in Power System- An Experience

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SUMMARY

The Indian electric power system is on a high growth phase and has expanded manifold. As on March 2018, POWERGRID have 148,838 ckm Transmission Lines, 236 Sub-Stations and 332,163 MVA Transformation Capacity.

There is a noticeable trend of utilities implementing Centralised Control Centers for Remote Operation of transmission system to improve the operational efficiency with reduced equipment downtime and to make utility more competitive. The centralised remote operation provides real time visibility and control of the transmission system, aiding quick restoration after a fault in comparison to the local operation being carried out from substation control room. Also, the comprehensive analysis and historical information helps in better asset management of the transmission system.

Faults in power systems are inevitable. Faults interrupt the power flow leading to economic loss and may also cause physical damage to the power system equipment. For precision in isolation of the fault, Numerical protection relays are being configured for various types of protection function like distance, differential, earth fault, over current, restricted earth fault etc for power system element i.e. Transmission line, Transformers & Reactors. These relays continuously monitor the system parameters and ensure the fast & precise isolation of the faulted element from the grid to ensure operational reliability and safety of the equipment. During the fault, the numerical relays also generate the disturbance record with pre fault & post fault values for the analysis of the incident.

Traditionally, protection engineers in a substation download the disturbance records (DR) & events from relays for manual analysis of the fault. These details are also sent to main office for broader analysis. The acquisition of disturbance records and its analysis for restoration of power system elements requires certain exposure as well as it is a time consuming process and also, it prohibits the fast decision making by operators at remote control centre. Thus, the need for development of a system was envisaged in POWERGRID.

Tools to analyse system conditions during fault and immediate transfer of DR files & events from various make & model of relays was a formidable challenge. This paper describes the application of Remote Accessibility System (RAS) & Automated Fault Analysis System (AFAS) for fault analysis in Power System which is implemented at POWERGRID for the first time globally. RAS-AFAS uses the communication capabilities of relays to share the DR files with identified devices over certain protocol. It provides the fault details to substation operators at remote control centres to take quick decision for restoration or otherwise of a transmission element in comparison to the traditional methodology of manual download of disturbance record file & manual analysis of fault by an expert. Thus, RAS-AFAS reduces the no. of experts placed at every station for local analysis, as expertise can be polled at centralised control centre only. The DR files of relays at substations is transmitted to the RAS server at remote control centre and the AFAS server analyses the incident based on the DR file shared by RAS server. In order to expedite the spread of information regarding the tripping of the power system element, the RAS-AFAS has been configured with the capability to send the email & SMS alerts to the concerned. Also, the appreciable features of remote access of relays from control centre and more precise fault location based on cumulative DR files from both ends of transmission line are available with RAS-AFAS system.

KEYWORDS

Remote Accessibility System-RAS, Automated Fault Analysis System-AFAS, Disturbance Record files-DR, automatic fault analysis reports, System Operation from remote control centre, Visualization of fault, Quick decision, Reduced outage time, Numerical protection relay, COMTRADE

1. BACKGROUND & MOTIVATION FOR RAS-AFAS

To overcome the challenging requirement of immediate availability of fault information at remote control centre, RAS-AFAS system was designed and broad comparison of fault analysis with traditional methodology is as follows:

Fault analysis with RAS-AFAS system	Traditional methodology of analysis
Automatically acquires the DR files from the substations numerical relays and transmits it to the remote servers located at control centre (In general, within 5 min after generation of DR file in the relay)	Usage of multiple relay specific configuration tools by substation Engineer to manually download the required DR files after connection to the relays individually.
Immediate availability of DR files and automated analysis report containing type of faults, distance of fault location, breaker operation analysis etc with operator at remote control centre for quick decision	Time consuming process of sharing the DR files and manual analysis report with operator
Immediate receipt of email as well as SMS alerts regarding the fault information to the concerned	Limited or delayed access of fault information
Automated analysis report gets generated based on predefined expert rules and template	Requirement of certain exposure to manually analyse the DR files
Availability of double end fault location based on cumulative DR files from both ends of the transmission line along with the single end fault locations.	Only single end fault location from both sides of transmission line is available

Other appreciable functionalities of RAS-AFAS system include the remote access of relays for reading relay logs & other parameters from control centre. Also, it avoids the possibility of loss of DR files from relay due to flushing of files because of limited storage in the relays. RAS-AFAS overview:

2. IMPLEMENTATION OF RAS-AFAS

Hardware used for RAS-AFAS implementation:

- i. RAS-AFAS Server: Installed at main & backup control centres
- ii. Substation Data Concentrator: Installed at each substation
- iii. Media & protocol converters: Installed at each substation
- iv. Ethernet switches & Serial Port Splitter: Installed at each substation for redundancy
- v. RAS-AFAS PC: Installed at each substation for local view at each substation & control centre

Redundancy of hardware & ports has been ensured at substation as well as control centre level.

System Architecture:

For integration of a substation with RAS-AFAS system, following activities are involved:

- a) Communication is to be established with various make & model of relays (IEC61850, IEC103, Courier, SPA & SEL) for auto collection of DR files.
- b) The collected DR files from relays are to be converted to COMTRADE format (if it is in proprietary format eg .areva, SPA etc).
- c) The COMTRADE format DR file is to be renamed with predefined naming convention and is to be forwarded to remote server at control centre.
- d) Protection relay database population & development is to be done at database server of control centre.
- e) Application server is to be configured with predefined expert rules to analyse the collected DR files based on developed database.
- f) Email addresses are to be configured to send the fault analysis report and similarly the groups of mobile no. are to be defined to SMS the fault summary in standard template.
- g) Configuration of application server for broader analysis (double end report, station level report) related to particular system event and to publish the report on web client.
- h) Configuration of RAS server to be done for remote access of relays for reading relay logs & other parameters from control centre.

Implementation challenges:

- i. Unique & customised design of software & hardware
- ii. First time implementation on large scale (~ 6500 no. relays of various make & model and protocol support) which results in multiple patches & fine tuning
- iii. Non-uniformity in signal names and type of Disturbance recorders
- iv. Choosing the right Algorithm depending upon the fault detected
- v. Management of multiple versions of relay specific configuration tool and restriction of multiple access of a particular relay
- vi. Partial configuration of relay communication port for data exchange on supported protocol

REPORT FOR :

EVENT ANALYZED

Report Type	Operator Report
Report ID	3231241
Region Name	ER02
Station Name	SUBHASHGRAM 400KV
Equipment	Transmission Line-400KV SUBHASHGRAM-SAGARDIGHI
Analysis Type	Single End
Relay Code	Main-1[ISTP1634011ER02]
Make and Model	AREVA MICOMP442
Trigger Date and Time	02/05/2018 11:05:24.864424
Fault Severity	Moderate

MiAFAS Analysis Summary

1. Fault Information

- R Phase to Ground Fault detected at 11:05:24.864424 Hrs (Dt: 02/05/2018) on 400kV 400KV SUBHASHGRAM-SAGARDIGHI
- The fault is calculated to be located at around 220.387 km from SUBHASHGRAM 400KV.
- During the incidence, maximum fault current of 1.73 kA and voltage dip of around 199 kV (0.86 pu) was recorded.

2. Line Trip / Auto Reclose Information

- DT was received at 11:05:25.156333 Hrs (799 ms after fault detection), on receipt of Direct Trip (DT) signal.
- No auto reclose action was detected.
- Opening of all three poles was recorded at 11:05:24.912167 Hrs (555 ms after fault detection).
- The line tripped at 11:05:25.106333 Hrs (749 ms after fault detection).

3. Relay Operation Information

- Zone 2 Trip was Obtained from Analog Zone Operation Analysis

Fault Details

Variable Name	Value
Fault Trigger Time	02/05/2018 11:05:24.864424
Fault Type	R Phase to Ground Fault
Fault Location (km)	220.387
Fault Current (kA)	1.725
Fault Voltage (kV)	199.510
Fault Impedance (Ohms)	12.779
Auto Reclosure	Not Attempted.
Fault Clearance Time (ms)	555.000
A/R Dead Time (ms)	NA
System Disturbance Time (ms)	749.166

2) Auto reclose not attempted case: Silchar-Azara line dated 02.05.2018 1:26

Line got tripped 3-phase at Silchar end on receipt of DT signal from other end. The remote operator got the DR file as well as report and executes successful manual charging attempt.

MiAFASTM
Automated Fault
Analysis System

File Name : 180502,012527922,IST,P191,4031,NER1

REPORT FOR :

EVENT ANALYZED

Report Type	Operator Report
Report ID	3229089
Region Name	NER1
Station Name	SILCHAR 400KV
Equipment	Transmission Line-400KV SILCHAR-AZARA
Analysis Type	Single End
Relay Code	Main-1[ISTP1914031NER1]
Make and Model	AREVA MICOMP444
Trigger Date and Time	02/05/2018 01:25:27.922000
Fault Severity	Moderate

MiAFAS Analysis Summary

1. Fault Information

- Y Phase to Ground Fault detected at 01:25:27.922000 Hrs (Dt: 02/05/2018) on 400kV 400KV SILCHAR-AZARA
- The fault is calculated to be located at around 158,215 km from SILCHAR 400KV.
- During the incidence, maximum fault current of 2.19 kA and voltage dip of around 155 kV (0.68 pu) was recorded.

2. Line Trip / Auto Reclose Information

- Line Tripped at 01:25:28.041667 Hrs (128 ms after fault detection), on receipt of Direct Trip (DT) signal.
- No auto reclose action was detected.

Fault at a Glance

Additionally, following benefits from RAS-AFAS are also obtained:

- Availability of collected DR files, events & statistical reports at control centre in a systematic manner & stored in hierarchical form.
- Better accuracy of Fault location based on cumulative DR files from both ends of transmission line (double end analysis)
- Web client access over VPN to substation and all control centre for accessing the data & reports in a secure manner
- Cumulative fault current for decision on breaker health
- Monitoring the pole open discrepancy of the breakers
- Monitoring of CVT errors & CT saturation

4. SCOPE FOR FUTURE ENHANCEMENT OF RAS-AFAS

System operators have had the first-hand experience of the benefits of RAS-AFAS with deployment done at 175 no. POWERGRID substations. The following enhancement may be considered as scope for future:

- Fault signature analysis
- Auto update of AFAS database from relay (similar to DR files) subject to standardization of relay setting template by each OEM
- Relay setting proposal based on pre-fault & post-fault condition of grid and regularity of fault occurrence.
- Since relay DR file sampling rate is generally 1000 samples per sec, the analysis accuracy (say fault location) may be increased with high sampling rate DR file.
- Integration of AFAS with PMU data.
- Update of actual details of fault in AFAS database by substation maintenance team for record & further fine tuning.
- Automatic reading of relay event logs & transfer to server at control centre
- Integration of RAS-AFAS with ERP for broader access

5. CONCLUSION

The paper has shared the POWERGRID experience of application of Remote Accessibility System & Automated Fault Analysis System for fault analysis in Power System. Other than the benefits outlined above in the paper, RAS-AFAS expedites the decision making to reduce the outage time of power system equipment. Thus, the implementation cost seems to be recovered within one year with full utilization of the system. Further, RAS-AFAS seems the next technological change to fulfill the requirement of rapidly growing power systems.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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- Working experience during the development, deployment & operation of RAS-AFAS from remote control centre under NTAMC project